

Polarographic Determination of Stability Constants of Ternary Complexes of Cadmium with α -Alanine as Primary Ligand and Oxalic Acid as Secondary Ligand

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Manuscript received 5 January 1987, revised 12 April 1988, accepted 25 April 1988

Polarographic technique was used to determine the values of solution stability of Cd- α -alaninate-oxalate system at pH 8.40 and ionic strength (μ) 1.0 M KNO₃. The reduction of the metal and its complexes was reversible and diffusion-controlled. Cd²⁺ forms two mixed complexes, viz. [Cd-(α -ala)-ox] and [Cd-(α -ala)₂-(ox)]²⁻ with α -alanine and oxalic acid at 42°. The values of stability constants are log β_{11} = 6.24 and log β_{21} = 9.23, respectively.

MOST of the amino acid compounds with different metals have great biological importance¹⁻⁵. Some ternary complexes of Cd²⁺ with amino acids and various organic acids have been reported from this laboratory^{4,5}. An up-to-date survey of literature shows no reference in the mixed-ligand complexes of α -alanine and oxalic acid with Cd²⁺ polarographically. Hence it was thought worthwhile to undertake the present investigation.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade and their solutions prepared in conductivity water. The concentrations of Cd²⁺, KNO₃ and gelatine in the test solution were 1.0 mM, 1.0 M and 0.01%, respectively.

The metal and ligands (oxalic acid and α -alanine) were taken in the ratio 1 : 40 and current-voltage curves were drawn at different pH values. The maximum shift of $E_{1/2}$ was observed at pH 8.40 (Fig. 5) and hence this pH was selected for the present investigation.

Current-voltage graphs were obtained on a Tinsley 120902 manual polarograph using a Toshniwal PL-50 polyflex galvanometer. The characteristics of capillary were $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.40 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$ at 60.0 cm effective height of mercury column. Purified nitrogen gas was passed through each test solution before recording the measurements. A Elico LI-10 needle type pH meter was used to measure pH of the test solution at 8.40. Dilute solution of sodium hydroxide and nitric acid were used to adjust the pH of the test solution. The entire study was carried out at 42°.

Results and Discussion

Cd²⁺ gives a well-defined two-electron reversible reduction wave in KNO₃. Single wave was observed in each set of solution. The plots of log $i/i_a - i$ vs E_a e. gives a straight line with slope $30 \pm 1 \text{ mV}$ (mean value) showing two-electron reversible reduction wave of Cd²⁺ and its complexes. A series of polarograms were obtained for binary complexes prior to the study of ternary complexes.

Fig. 1. Values of $F_4 [X]$ for Cd- α -ala medium.

Cd- α -alaninate system : The pK_a (2.50) and pK_b (9.40) values of α -alanine were calculated by titration method⁷. α -Alanine is a dipolar ion

${}^+\text{H}_2\text{N}-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)-\text{COO}^-$ which ionises in water as¹

its $\text{p}K_a$ that refers the acidity of an ammonium ion, RNH_3^+ is

$$K_a = \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{O}^+][\text{H}_2\text{NCHCH}_3\text{COO}^-]}{[{}^+\text{H}_2\text{NCHCH}_3\text{COO}^-]}$$

and $\text{p}K_b$, which refers the basicity of a carboxylic ion RCOO^- is given as

Basic function

$$K_b = \frac{[{}^+\text{H}_2\text{NCHCH}_3\text{COOH}][\text{OH}^-]}{[{}^+\text{H}_2\text{NCHCH}_3\text{COO}^-]}$$

when the solution of α -alanine is made alkaline, it is converted into the anion $[\text{H}_2\text{NCHCH}_3\text{COO}^-]$ as

The free ligand concentrations $[\text{H}_2\text{NCHCH}_3\text{COO}^-]$ were calculated from $\text{p}K_b$ and pH values of the test solution. The present study has been carried out at pH 8.40. The values of half-wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) shifted to more negative values on increasing the concentration of α -alanine. The nature of all the waves were reversible and diffusion-controlled. The method of Deford and Hume² was applied to confirm the formation of three complexes, viz. $[\text{Cd}(\alpha\text{-ala})]^+$, $[\text{Cd}(\alpha\text{-ala})_2]$ and $[\text{Cd}(\alpha\text{-ala})_3]^-$; their values of stability constants are $\log \beta_{10} = 4.17$, $\log \beta_{20} = 6.60$ and $\log \beta_{30} = 9.95$, respectively at 42°. The plots of $F_4[X]$ vs $[\alpha\text{-ala}]$ and the data are given in Fig. 1 and Table 1, respectively.

Cd-oxalate system: The concentration of ligand in the test solution varied from 1.0 to 10.0 mM at pH 8.40 and $\mu = 1.0 \text{ M KNO}_3$. The concentrations

of Cd^{2+} and gelatine were 1.0 mM and 0.01%, respectively. Each wave was reversible and diffusion-controlled which was confirmed from the values ($E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$) = $30 \pm 1 \text{ mV}$ (mean value). The plots of $F_4[Y]$ vs $[\text{ox}^{2-}]$ (Fig. 2) confirmed the formation of three complexes, viz. $[\text{Cd}(\text{ox})]$, $[\text{Cd}(\text{ox})_2]^{2-}$ and $[\text{Cd}(\text{ox})_3]^{4-}$ with stability constants $\log \beta_{01} = 2.00$, $\log \beta_{02} = 4.69$ and $\log \beta_{03} = 7.08$, respectively. The results are given in Table 2.

Fig. 2. Values of $F_4[Y]$ for Cd-ox medium.

Cd- α -alaninate oxalate-system: The system was studied at pH 8.40 and $\mu = 1.0 \text{ M KNO}_3$. The concentration of $[\text{H}_2\text{NCHCH}_3\text{COO}^-]$ was varied from 1.0 to 10.0 mM while the concentration of oxalic acid was fixed at 0.005 and 0.01 M and current-voltage-graphs were plotted. Each wave was reversible and diffusion-controlled. A method of Schapp and McMaster³ revealed the formation of $[\text{Cd}-(\alpha\text{-ala})-(\text{ox})]^-$ and $[\text{Cd}(\alpha\text{-ala})_2-(\text{ox})]^{2-}$ complexes with stability constants $\log \beta_{11} = 6.24$ and $\log \beta_{21} = 9.23$, respectively. The values of constants A, B, C and D at two different concentrations of oxalic acid are given in Figs. 3 and 4, and the data in Tables 2 and 3.

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND $F_4[X]$ VALUES FOR Cd- α -ALANINATE SYSTEM

$[\alpha\text{-ala}]$ M	$\Delta E_{1/2}$ V	$\log I_m/I_0$	$F_0[X]$	$F_1[X]$ $\times 10^4$	$F_2[X]$ $\times 10^6$	$F_3[X]$ $\times 10^8$
0.00	—	—	1.00	—	—	—
0.001	0.037	0.014 4	18.47	1.74	—	—
0.002	0.060	0.021 9	112.79	5.59	20.44	8.22
0.003	0.074	0.029 4	341.63	11.35	32.84	9.61
0.004	0.081	0.029 4	589.44	14.11	33.02	7.25
0.005	0.092	0.029 4	1388.92	27.76	52.51	9.70
0.006	0.100	0.037 1	2087.27	34.77	55.45	8.75
0.007	0.104	0.037 1	3601.30	51.43	71.33	9.61
0.008	0.110	0.044 9	5851.94	73.13	89.54	10.69
0.010	0.115	0.044 9	8639.72	86.38	—	—

$$\log \beta_{10} = 4.17$$

$$\log \beta_{20} = 6.60$$

$$\log \beta_{30} = 9.95$$

Fig 3 Values of $F_{0j}[X, Y]$, for Cd- α -ala-ox system when $A=5.0, B=2.0 \times 10^4, C=15 \times 10^6$ and $D=9.0 \times 10^9$.

Fig 4. Values of $F_{0j}[X, Y]$ for Cd- α -ala-ox system when $A=2.00, B=4.0 \times 10^4, G=16 \times 10^6$ and $D=15 \times 10^9$

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND $F_j[Y]$ VALUES FOR [Cd-ox] SYSTEM

[Cd²⁺] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ M, μ = 1.0 M KNO₃, pH = 8.40, Temp = 42°
 $E_{1/2}$ of Cd²⁺ = -0.610 V vs SCE

[ox ²⁻] M	$\Delta E_{1/2}$ V	log I_m/I_0	$F_0[Y]$	$F_1[Y]$ × 10 ³	$F_2^2[Y]$ × 10 ⁴	$F_3[Y]$ × 10 ⁷
0.00	—	—	1.00	—	—	—
0.001	0.003	0.000	1.16	1.60	6.00	1.00
0.002	0.005	0.007	1.50	2.50	7.50	1.25
0.003	0.008	0.014	1.92	3.06	—	—
0.004	0.013	0.014	2.84	4.60	9.00	1.00
0.005	0.018	0.021	4.27	6.55	11.10	2.00
0.006	0.022	0.029	5.94	8.23	12.05	1.17
0.007	0.028	0.029	9.48	12.11	15.88	1.55
0.008	0.035	0.029	16.36	19.20	22.75	2.21
0.010	0.054	0.037	73.19	72.19	71.19	—

log β_{10} = 2.00 log β_{02} = 4.69 log β_{03} = 7.08

TABLE 3—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND $F_{0j}[X, Y]$ VALUES FOR [Cd- α -ala-ox] SYSTEM

[ox] = 0.005 M (fixed), μ = 1.0 M KNO₃, pH = 8.40, Temp. = 42°
 $E_{1/2}$ of Cd²⁺ = -0.610 V vs SCE

[α -ala] M	$\Delta E_{1/2}$ V	log I_m/I_0	$F_{00}[X, Y]$	$F_{10}[X, Y]$ × 10 ³	$F_{20}[X, Y]$ × 10 ⁴	$F_{30}[X, Y]$ × 10 ⁷
0.000	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.001	0.041	0.014	25.22	20.22	—	—
0.002	0.061	0.021	121.93	58.46	19.23	9.05
0.003	0.075	0.021	362.99	119.33	33.11	7.28
0.004	0.085	0.021	791.22	196.55	44.13	9.14
0.005	0.094	0.029	1623.15	323.63	60.72	9.41
0.006	0.100	0.029	2590.99	430.93	71.48	8.78
0.007	0.105	0.037	3893.13	555.44	76.49	10.92
0.008	0.112	0.037	6117.07	839.00	102.37	9.01
0.010	0.118	0.037	10720.62	1071.56	105.15	—

log A = 0.69 log B = 4.30 log C = 7.17 log D = 9.95

TABLE 4—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND F_{ij} [X, Y] VALUES FOR [Cd- α -ala-ox]

[ox] = 0.01 M (fixed), μ = 1.0 M KNO₃, pH = 8.40, Temp. = 42°
 $E_{1/2}$ of Cd²⁺ = -0.610 V vs SCE

[α -ala] M	$\Delta E_{1/2}$ V	log I_m/I_0	F_{00} [X, Y]	F_{10} [X, Y] $\times 10^2$	F_{20} [X, Y] $\times 10^6$	F_{30} [X, Y] $\times 10^6$
0.00	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.001	0.053	0.021 9	65.37	45.37	—	—
0.002	0.065	0.021 9	166.53	73.26	16.63	—
0.003	0.080	0.021 9	535.92	171.97	43.99	9.33
0.004	0.088	0.037 1	1 035.18	253.79	53.44	9.36
0.005	0.100	0.037 1	2 636.93	523.38	96.67	16.13
0.006	0.105	0.037 1	3 893.13	645.52	107.58	15.26
0.007	0.111	0.044 9	6 326.15	900.87	122.98	15.28
0.008	0.116	0.044 9	9 339.85	1 164.98	145.61	16.20
0.010	0.120	0.052 9	12 992.71	1 297.27	—	—

log A = 1.30 log B = 4.60 log C = 7.20 log D = 10.17

Fig. 5. (a) Cd- α -ala (1 : 40), (b) Cd-ox (1 : 40) and (c) Cd- α -ala-ox (1 : 40 : 40) systems.

The systems Cd- α -alaninate, Cd-oxalate and Cd-(α -alaninate)-oxalate have also been studied at higher concentration of reactants specially ligands and at higher ionic strength but the best results were obtained at $\mu=1.0$ M KNO₃ and concentration of [α -ala] and [ox] from 0.001 to 0.01 M at pH 8.40. The systems [Cd- α -ala] (Fig. 5a) and

[Cd- α -ala-ox] (Fig. 5c) show remarkable change in $E_{1/2}$ with pH but the system [Cd-ox] (Fig. 5b) shows smaller change in $E_{1/2}$ with pH, because oxalic acid is a weaker ligand as compared to glycine. The change in $E_{1/2}$ with the addition of secondary ligand, i.e. oxalic acid, to the binary system [Cd- α -ala], confirms that the ternary complexes are formed (Fig. 5)^{6,10}.

For a comparison of the stabilities of simple and mixed complexes, it is convenient to calculate¹¹ the value of log K_m from the relation,

$$\log K_m = \log \beta_{11} - 1/2 [\log \beta_{20} + \log \beta_{02}]$$

which is equal to 0.599. The positive value of log K_m shows that mixed complexes [Cd- α -ala-ox]⁻ is more stable than the simple binary complexes of Cd²⁺ with α -alanine and oxalic acid.

The values of log β_{11} (6.24) and log β_{21} (9.2¹) are in good agreement with the calculated values of log β_{11} (6.45) and log β_{21} (9.47) obtained by Watter and Dewitt equations¹². The results of the present study have been summarised below,

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to Dr. S. P. Banerjee, Prof. and Head, Department of Chemistry, for the facilities.

References

1. R. T. MORRISON and R. N. BOYD, "Organic Chemistry", 4th. ed., Allyn & Bacon, London, 1959, pp. 1118-1122.
2. W. F. STACK and H. A. SKINNER, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1967, **63**, 1136.
3. G. BEECH, *Quart. Rev. Chem.*, 1970, **23**, 410.
4. K. NEMA and F. KHAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, **1987**, **64**, 629.
5. F. KHAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, communicated.
6. D. N. HUME, D. D. DEFORD and G. C. B. CAVE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5325.
7. S. CHABEREK and A. E. MARTEL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 5052.
8. D. DEFORD and D. N. HUME, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5312.
9. W. B. SCHAAP and D. L. MCMASTER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4999.
10. M. A. GHANDOUR, A. A. EL-SAMAHY and Z. KOMY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **62**, 198.
11. V. V. RAMANUJAM and U. KRISHNAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 425.
12. J. I. WATTERS and R. DEWITT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 1333.